

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cd(II)-Diethylenetriamine Pentaacetic Acid and Tartaric Acid : A Polarographic Study

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Cd(II)-DTPA-tartaric acid mixed system has been examined polarographically. The reduction of the complex is reversible. The complex species $[Cd(II)-DTPA]^{2-}$, $[Cd(II)-TA]$ and $[Cd(II)-DTPA-TA]^{6-}$ have been observed in the system. The value of equilibrium constant for the mixed system was found to be $\log \beta_{11} = 4.05$.

LITERATURE reveals that detailed study of mixed ligand complexes of some transition metal ions has been made, using pH-metric¹, potentiometric² and various other techniques³⁻⁵. However, after the work of Schaap and McMasters⁶ the polarographic technique has also received considerable attention in this field. Recently, mixed ligand complexes of some transition metals have been studied polarographically⁷. The results of polarographic study on the Cd(II)-DTPA-tartrate system are presented here.

Experimental

B.D.H., AnalaR grade chemicals were used. The solutions used for the study were prepared in double distilled water. A C.I.C., Baroda automatic pen recording polarograph was used to record the polarograms and an Elico digital pH meter was used to record the pH of the solutions. Potassium chloride (1.0 M) was used as supporting electrolyte and also to adjust the ionic strength of the experimental sets at $\mu=1.0$. Purified nitrogen gas was bubbled through the test solutions for 15 min before recording the polarograms. All the observations were made at $22.5 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The capillary had the 'm' value = 2.373 mg/sec, drop time = 3.0 sec, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ in 1.0 M potassium chloride at -0.7 V vs SCE at 45 cm effective height of mercury column.

The pH of the test solutions were fixed at 1.8 with required quantity of HCl or NaOH solutions.

Results and Discussion

Simple Cd(II)-DTPA and Cd(II)-tartrate systems were investigated polarographically and the Cd(II)-DTPA-tartrate system was also studied under identical experimental conditions.

The reduction of pure metal and its complexes (binary and ternary) under study was found to be of diffusion controlled nature as is shown by the

linear relationship between the diffusion current and the square root of the effective height of mercury column which pass through the origin. The electrode reaction was observed to be reversible involving two electrons which is evident from the slope values of the log plots which are $30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$.

Polarography of Cd(II)-DTPA system: In each experimental set, the concentration of potassium chloride, Cd(II) and gelatin was kept constant at 1.0 M, 2 mM and 0.001%, respectively. The concentration of DTPA was varied from 1 mM to 100 mM. A Lingane⁸ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 Cd(II)-DTPA complex with its formation constant equal to $\log \beta_{10} = 2.96$.

Polarography of Cd(II)-tartrate system: The concentration of potassium chloride, Cd(II) and gelatin was kept constant at 1.0 M, 2 mM and 0.001%, respectively in each experimental set. The concentration of tartaric acid was varied from 1 mM to 100 mM. A Lingane⁸ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 Cd(II)-tartrate complex with its formation constant equal to $\log \beta_{10} = 2.41$.

Polarography of Cd(II)-DTPA-tartrate mixed systems: For the study of mixed complex system, the concentration of potassium chloride, metal ion and gelatin was fixed as above and the concentration of the weaker ligand, tartaric acid, was fixed at 50 mM. The concentration of DTPA was varied from 10 mM to 0.5 M. The polarograms for each set were recorded.

It is observed that the shift in $E_{1/2}$ of Cd(II) towards negative value is more in presence of DTPA and tartrate ions than in tartrate ion alone. This clearly indicates the formation of Cd(II)-DTPA-tartrate mixed complex. The polarographic data of F_{ij} functions of the ternary complex at a fixed concentration of tartaric acid have been tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1— F_{11} AS A FUNCTION OF DTPA
 $Cd^{2+}=2\text{ mM}$, $\mu=1.0M(KCl)$, $pH=1.80+0.01$
 Tartaric acid = 50 mM, $E_{1/2}$ of $Cd^{2+} = -0.64\text{ V}$ vs SCE, drop time = 3.0 sec

DTPA M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	$\log I_M/I_C$	Slope mV	$F_{0.0}$	$F_{1.0} \times 10^3$	$F_{2.0} \times 10^4$
0.000						—
0.001	0.012	0.010	32	3.55	1.00	
0.002	0.025	0.015	30	8.01	2.73	8.75
0.005	0.035	0.017	31	17.94	3.09	4.22
0.008	0.045	0.019	29	48.00	5.68	5.87
0.010	0.050	0.020	32	84.12	8.157	7.177
0.015	0.060	0.022	32	180.28	11.84	7.24
0.020	0.068	0.022	31	290	14.37	6.695

A = 2.55 ; B = 980 ; $\log \beta_{11} = 4.05$.

A Schaap and McMasters treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 Cd-DTPA-tartrate mixed complex with $\log \beta_{11}$ value = 4.05.

A schematic representation of formation of the mixed complex is shown below :

It is quite clear from the equilibrium constant value that the ternary complex is more stable than either of the two binary complexes.

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